

INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY, GOOD GOVERNANCE, AND NATIONAL SECURITY

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Abstract

Information Communication Technology has become a veritable tool for Human development. However, despite its numerous advantages in the realm of Utility, yet it has inherent consequences that portend ills in the realm of good governance and national security. In conclusion, considering the foregoing, ICT plays "dual" roles in good governance and national security. Besides, its effectiveness in our dear country cannot be underestimated in view of the globalization trends. These are examined in this paper with recommendations on how the negative consequences could be addressed to enhance good governance and a stable polity. Also, government should tackle the problem of youth graduate unemployment with all the resources available. It should be noted that unemployment has thrown many youths to take up arms as arm robbers or join the insurgents as a means of survival. If government open jobs in various sectors of the Nigerian economy coupled with zero level for corruption and bribery, good governance will yield the desired results.

Introduction

Information Communication and Technology (ICT) is the processing and maintenance of information and the use of all forms of computer, communication network and mobile technologies to transmit information (Yusuf, 2012). Communication technologies encompasses all media employed in transmitting audio, video, data, or multimedia such as cable satellite, fiber optics, wireless (radio infra-red, blue tooth, Wi-fi). Network technologies include Personal Area Network (PAN), Campus Area Network (CAN), Internets extranets LANS, WANS, MANS and the internet (Lawal, 2014). The rapid growth in Information Communication and Technology (ICT) have brought remarkable changes in the twenty-first century, as well as affected the demands of modern societies (Adebayo, 2010). ICT is becoming increasingly important in our society in our daily lives and in our educational system. Therefore, ICT has turned the whole world to a global village. The impact of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) on learning in relation to the use of digital media, primarily computers and internet to facilitate teaching and learning has become an undisputed asset in our educational system

(Yusuf, 2012). ICTs are the technologies used in conveying, manipulating, and storing of something is missing here by electronic means. They provide powerful tools that may help in transforming the present isolated teaching into rich student focused interactive knowledge environments Adebayo (2016) and Oyebanji (2017).

Information communication technology can be explained to mean the science of storing information through electronic devices and making such information available to the users wherever it is required. In other words, it is the method and technical means of capturing, storing, processing, retrieving, and transmitting data (knowledge through multi-media electronic-based approach), (Abdullahi, 2019). While information deals with conceived ideas by human mind that needs to be communicated with the use of science products Communication on the other hand is the transfer of information from the original source to the destination where it is needed with the aim of producing changes in behavior of the learner. (Oniye, Yahaya & Alawaye, 2020). Technology on the other hand is seen as a process of dealing with materials as to assure mastery of mankind over physical control

mechanisms, 'both human' and non-human. Hence whenever a systematic plan is developed and carried out to successfully communicate facts, ideas, beliefs, behaviours or knowledge technology has taken place (Adebayo, 2016.)

The incorporation and use of ICT in Nigeria schools articulated by the adoption of Education for all (EFA) in the National policy of Education is a way in accelerating social, scientific, political, and technological progress. More so, the pragmatic approach undertaken by the Federal government in the National policy on ICT has liberalized IT, which has brought veritable revolution in the country. This has led to the emergence of global network services represented by MTN, GLO, Airtel- that provides relatively cheaper and affordable telephone network services nationally and internationally (Adebayo, 2018).

ICT as exemplified by broadcast media also serve as means to transmit ideas, information, attitudes, and opinions to audience via the use of air waves. This forum permits the dissemination of information through audio- radio and audio-visual television which are characteristically unique from other electronic media because of the way they distribute signals to several audiences at the same time. This makes the presentation of information with a sense of immediacy possible how it happens at the same time it is unfolding (Dike, 2018). Today, the integration of ICT has brought about the evolution of information technology which is speedily growing and touching every aspect of human endeavours, be it educational, economical political- good or bad governance, social and even the religious aspect of man. Infact ICT influences is said to have turned the whole world to a global village (Abifarin, 2020).

According to Fadeyiye (2017) Technological tools are nowadays used to educate, entertain, inform, mobilize, and play articulatory roles by linking government with the governed. More so, they could also be used to make or mar the progress, development, and destiny of a nation. In support of this Adesoji (2017) asserted that Radio and television are potent and dynamic instruments for shaping and monitoring the electoral process of a nation and their greatest advantage lie in their wide coverage. However, the reality on ground in Nigeria shows

that the country is still far from utilizing technologies for attaining good governance by what good governance stands for.

Good Governance

It is evident that countries in the world have now been classified on basis of their invention and use of scientific approaches in the realm of developments. Hence Nigeria is being classified as a developing country and is in league of utilizing tools, materials, techniques, and sources of power that tends to make life and work easier (Adebayo, 2016). In this context, technological innovations such as in the print/ electronic media, internet facilities, mobile phones, military hard wares etc serves as pivotal technological sources which are fundamental to the development and survival of Nigeria nation. It is a truism that good governance implies process whereby public institutions conduct public affairs, manage public resources, and guarantee human freedom from abuse yet, does this occur in Nigeria? Good governance is also said to be the absence of corruption, strict adherence to accountability, absence of excessive military influences, lack of threat to life and property, freedom of speech and expression of dissenting voices, and citizens live at peace with minimal level of comfort.

National Security

A nation where the fundamental rights and privileges of her citizenry are not protected both internal and external is said to be experiencing a National Security threat whereas Wikipedia (2012) opined that National Security is the requirement to maintain the survival of the state through the use of economic diplomatic power projection and political powers. The concept developed mostly in the United State of America after World War II. initially it focuses on military right, it now encompasses a broad range facet, all of which impinge on the non-military or economic security of the nation and the value response by the National Society.

However, on daily basis Nigerian witness hazards, and threats to individuals and corporate existence. This is evidence in various cases of Arm- robberies (Banks outside Ilorin have closed shop for over five months because of incessant raids) kidnappings, ethno-religious crisis, military

and of wider dimension is the activities of the dreaded Boko-Haram insurgents whose operation is threatening the corporate existence of Nigeria (Adebayo, 2018). All these irregularities are evidence of failed governance of the Nigerian states, because, it appears, the political leaders are not in reality exercising the power and authority, political, economic administrative or otherwise as to articulate process and practice to promote good governance in Nigeria. (Adebayo, 2018). National security problem is not limited to Nigeria, this phenomenon is a global trend that is prevalent internationally, for instance Israel and Hama at war, Egypt is embroiled with civil war, with insurgents, also Kenya, Somalia, and Sudan etc., also are involved in wars. However, insecurity challenges in Nigeria seem to be growing daily due to the prevalence of political gangsters, illegal arms dealing, oil bunkering. Internet frauds all which portends fragility of the nation and makes Nigeria a dangerous investment environment for investors (Onwilbiko, 2016). It cannot be over sighted to mention governments' efforts at combating the issue of insecurity in the nation. One notes various government involvement by way of providing logistics, vehicles, military equipment, etc, yet the hydra-headed nature of insecurity seems to be insurmountable as these interventions are not pragmatic enough

Consequently, national security is very important in all facets of human life. Without a secured system and environment, education and other aspect of human growth and development cannot thrive. Hence, for us to attain an effective teacher education system, there is the need for our political class and communities' leaders to enhance conducive, safe, comfortable, and warm atmosphere where the training can take place, devoid of any internal or external threat. Iyanda, (2017) equally summarized the effects of lack of adequate and effective teacher education which can 'mar' or "make" our national security functional:

- Inadequate education is gradually eroding the culture of self-respect and dignity for labour.
- The family standard of adequate education is beginning to promote violent in actualization of self-desires.
- The desire to search for knowledge is drastically reducing among the people. People do not see knowledge as power any

longer; hence many takes to the part of violent that leads to destruction.

- Lack of adequate education has also increased the desire for reckless risk taking expressed in violent. There is adventurism in violent risk to get to the top. Parents hail their children when they involve in violent and even share out of the outcome of the shameful and disgraceful violent displays.

Lack of adequate education has unfortunately increased the problems of violent and insecurity in Nigeria.

Technology Good Governance and National Security

Evidence abounds worldwide that technology- invention and use of scientific approaches is a yardstick for classifying nations. In the Nigerian policy, technology plays vital roles in various shares of human endeavours. In the Nigerian content, the innovation has tremendous influence on teaching and learning, because through its dynamic, interactive, flexible, and engaging content, it enhances faster knowledge transfer especially through simulations and animation. More so, ICT has potentials to accelerate, enrich and deepen skills to motivate and engage students in learning, relate such experiences to work practices create economic inability for tomorrow work, contribute to radical changes in school activities, strengthen teaching and provide opportunities for connections between the school and the rapid technological social, political and economic transformations (Oniye et al. 2016).

In view of the foregoing, the use of technology in governance and national security is paramount. It should be noted that the print media an arm of technology is often referred to as the fourth estate of government. This is in recognition of the press and its inherent abilities to disseminating information of various kinds to every look and corner of the country. In the realm of broadcast media (radio and Television), notable political propagandas, religion teaching-drama, crusades and musical activities, sports of international dimensions dominate the air waves These activities have proved to easily influence the populace orientations audibly and visibly in colour at the same time. The availability and use of

mobile phones, and internet facilities makes dissemination of information- "news" to go world-wide. This makes happenings to be heard and seen simultaneously as such events are unfolding. The use of satellite transmission to transmit or broadcast live events cannot be over sighted. This innovation has gone a long way to aid distance learning in schools, banks, and security agencies. Everybody interprets and responds to the influence of ICT differently, but there is a need to examine critically what it does for the nation especially its hyperemic syringe effects-negative effects especially in the realm of good governance and national security.

Advances in the realm of technology have influenced our social values as practiced by our forefathers. In this vein Awolalu (2019) opines that advances in technology have led to a decline in faith and potency of prayer, as different types of miracles of old no longer happen. Also, many things earlier attributed to the realm of mystery no longer pose mysterious hence people are far removed from the security of the village. According to Kumuyi, (2018) technological innovations seem to bring evils to religions(s) especially the advent of television and video. He asserted that the potentials of their conveying thoughts in pictures, colour, language and motion increases engagements in entertainments and pleasure. This he claimed impresses some vices on the mind of the youth; making light violence, hooliganism, murder, rape, assault, bribery, corruption, bombing, suicide bombers and other sins condemned by religions. In view of this the national security of Nigeria is under threat as youth and leaders are exposed daily to evil deeds and influenced by ICT that facilitate moral decadence hitting the fabric of our nation. (Adebayo, 2016) ICT has helped to spread ideas, thoughts, and philosophy of adherents of various religious faithful. However, such has facilitated the production of weapons of human destruction to eliminate enemies of religions (Oladejo, 2017). This is true as procedure for local production of explosives abounds on internet websites, through which untrained but computer literate militants/insurgents adapt and adopt to produce explosives which have been used in many parts of Nigeria leading to loss of lives and destruction of properties. The use of ICT in terrorist's enclaves is also predominant. They often use internet to

spread pictures and video of terrorist activities and distribute messages, and for training information. More so, many of such organizations have effectively utilized international media to enhance their attacks as images of horror are distributed to the public (Mark, 2016).

Conclusion

Considering the foregoing, ICT plays "dual" roles in good governance and national security. Besides, its effectiveness in our dear country cannot be underestimated in view of the globalization trends. However, there are some inherent contradictions which demands that government(s) should take salient steps to stem the pace of its incongruous application to promote good governance and enhance national security. It was concluded from the findings that Information Communication and Technology has positive influence on secondary school education through impacting student's level of social integration, information search and practice, improved students' academic performance, teachers teaching skills and in the attainment of educational policy and curriculum implementation practices.

Thus, it is recommended that religions leaders, teachers and the media should utilize technological innovations to teach and preach religious tolerance, as intolerance is the bane of religious crisis, which is tantamount to national insecurity that jeopardizes good governance. Government should ensure that TV and radio programmes are well censored as not to promote social vices that run contrary to religious teachings. Films on crimes, violence, nudity, and pornography on internet sites should be banned from public viewing. Government should tackle the problem of youth graduate unemployment with all the resources available. It should be noted that unemployment has thrown many youths to take up arms as arm robbers or join the insurgents as a means of survival. If government opens jobs in various sectors of the Nigerian economy coupled with zero level for corruption and bribery. Good governance will yield the desired results. Finally, this paper does not pretend to be an exhaustible treatment of the roles of ICT in Good governance and national security but takes consonance of its benefits- and contradictory roles which threatens national security. It is believed

that stakeholders in politics and peace experts will note and adopt appropriately ICT innovations to promote good governance and National security.

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